

BIT BY BIT: A RAPID ASSESSMENT METHODOLOGY FOR EVALUATING FILE FORMAT OBSOLESCENCE RISK

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Abstract – In this paper I provide a practical rapid-assessment methodology for determining whether a preservation intervention is recommended based upon a prioritized, sequential list of positive and negative file format obsolescence risk factors.

Rather than a complex scoring system, the core output of this methodology is a simple set of conditions that aim to suit general use-cases for quickly determining whether a given format is at immediate risk of obsolescence and therefore whether an immediate preservation intervention is required.

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I. INTRODUCTION

There have been many methodologies created to quantify file format obsolescence risk, commonly using systems where scores are assigned to different categories, with an overall score calculated and measured against some threshold [1] [2] [3] [4].

Such scoring systems can be highly resource intensive to use and can require extensive research to determine precisely where on a scale a given file format lies for a given factor.

Further, the criteria scoring, and the score weighting that is often a component of such approaches, can be susceptible to subjective

interpretation and therefore may result in inconsistent conclusions regarding format risk.

As an alternative to these methodologies, I offer a general-purpose and domain-independent assessment methodology based on a list of binary conditions that can be objectively assessed and used to rapidly determine whether a file format represents an immediate obsolescence risk and whether a preservation intervention is recommended.

The list is intended to be considered on a sequential, exit-early basis so if, for example, condition 1 is met, then no further conditions need to be considered. Some conditions are positive, meaning no preservation intervention is currently recommended, while some are negative, meaning a preservation intervention is recommended.

While Preservica's preservation interventions are typically focused on file format migration, this methodology is neutral on preservation interventions and outcomes. A valid preservation intervention could involve the urgent acquisition of appropriate first-party or third-party software that could support an at-risk format.

II. THE CONDITIONS

The conditions listed below are in priority order and where a condition is met, the list can be exited without considering further factors.

1) Any file format where the format maintainers have themselves declared that the format's ongoing use poses a security vulnerability, or the format is or will soon be end-of-life, unsupported, or otherwise superseded where they recommend moving to an alternative file format, shall be considered at risk and a preservation intervention is recommended.

2) Any file format which can be opened in a fresh installation of a current version of Microsoft Windows or MacOS without the need to install additional software, shall not be considered at risk at this time and a preservation intervention is unnecessary.

3) Any file format currently associated with an established, recognized standards body, shall not be considered at risk at this time and a preservation intervention is unnecessary.

4) Any file format currently associated with an established, recognized foundational body for free and open-source software, shall not be considered at risk at this time and a preservation intervention is unnecessary.

5) Any file format primarily associated with a specific software application where its native first-party software is no longer available through standard means, such as retail or through a supported open-source release, except in cases where a direct successor software product is available, shall be considered at risk and a preservation intervention is recommended.

6) In cases where a direct successor software product is available, any file format which cannot be opened by the current generation of its own native first-party software without extensions, plug-ins, or other workarounds, shall be considered at risk and a preservation intervention is recommended.

7) Any file format that previously had a dedicated, official web presence, such as a standalone web site, or a web page or specification published on its vendor's website, that is no longer available or is only now available via an internet archive, shall be considered at risk and a preservation intervention is recommended.

8) Any file format that has never had a dedicated, official web presence, shall be considered at risk and a preservation intervention is recommended.

III. RATIONALE AND EXAMPLES

The rationale for each condition is described below.

1) If the format vendors themselves are recommending no longer using the format, then this represents a clear obsolescence risk.

Note that as the highest priority condition, this condition takes precedence over other conditions, so a file format that was published by a standards body, but which has since been designated as obsolete or superseded by those involved would still be considered at risk and a preservation intervention recommended.

File format examples include Microsoft Publisher, which Microsoft has announced will be removed from Office 365 in October 2026 [5], Smacker video, whose vendor Rad Game Tools now suggests using Bink video instead [6], and Free Lossless Image Format (FLIF), which has ultimately been superseded by JPEG-XL [7].

2) If a file format can be opened using the native applications supplied out-of-the-box with either of the two most popular desktop operating systems, then this implies they have reached such ubiquity that they are unlikely to represent an obsolescence risk any time soon.

File format examples include GIF, QuickTime MOV, AVI.

3) Where a file format is backed by a well-established and recognized standards body rather than a single vendor then this implies a depth of support such that they are unlikely to represent an obsolescence risk any time soon.

Examples of such bodies include the International Standards Organization (ISO), the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF), and the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST). It is recognized that individuals and institutions may place more trust or value in some standards bodies than others.

In the event that any such body ceases operation then all file formats under their custodianship would be considered at risk under condition 1.

File format examples include JPEG-2000 [8], MXF [9], MPEG-4 [10].

4) Where a file format is backed by a well-established and recognized foundational body for free and open-source software rather than a single vendor then this implies a depth of support such that they are unlikely to represent an obsolescence risk any time soon.

Examples of such bodies include The Apache Software Foundation, The Xiph Foundation, and The Document Foundation. It is recognized that individuals and institutions may place more trust or value in some open-source bodies than others.

In the event that any such body ceases operation then all file formats under their custodianship would be considered at risk under condition 1.

File format examples include Ogg media formats [11], FLAC [12], APNG [13].

5) Where a file format's native first-party software is no longer available through official channels, such as retail, direct purchase, or through an official and currently supported download webpage, then it is likely to be at risk, even where third-party software may continue to render such formats.

File format examples include DeluxePaint ANM Animation, Seattle FilmWorks SFW Image, Silicon Graphics Image, all of which were primarily associated with first-party software that is now discontinued.

6) Where the direct successor to a file format's native first-party software cannot open the format without additional intervention, such as the installation of patches or plug-ins, then this is likely to be at risk, even where third-party software may continue to render such formats.

File format examples include early versions of RealAudio, which do not render using a current version of RealPlayer, DOS versions of Microsoft Word, which cannot be opened using a current version of Office 365, and AppleWorks documents, which cannot be opened using a current version of Apple Pages.

7) When new file formats are launched, whether as a standalone specification or library, tied to a new software or hardware product, or as a result of a collaboration between vendors to create a mutually compatible file format, it is common to see a web

page or website created to publicize the format and to describe its features, or otherwise to promote the associated software or hardware product.

When such a web presence has been deleted or otherwise disappeared from the web (or is only available via a web archive), perhaps due to the expiry of the web domain, then this can indicate that the format vendors are no longer invested in the format.

This could be considered analogous to condition 1, but where the withdrawal of support is implicit rather than explicitly stated.

File format examples include TrueAudio, whose website is now occupied by cyber-squatters, Sony ATRAC, whose webpage is now removed from the Sony website, and Shorten Audio, whose website has disappeared.

8) Where a file format or its native first-party software has never had any kind of web presence, most likely due to pre-dating the rise of the worldwide web, then this can be considered at risk.

IV. FURTHER CONSIDERATIONS

This is a generalized set of conditions, but there are local factors that may warrant additional consideration, and practitioners may wish to extend this methodology to suit their local use-cases.

1) The increasing awareness and focus on IT security means that many institutions are adopting Approved Software Lists (ASLs) that determine which software is allowed to be installed on a given network or IT system.

The use of ASLs may result in preservation institutions holding data in file formats that are not generally considered to be at risk in accordance with the conditions above, but which their own IT security policies impede being worked with in their native software environment due to exclusion from the approved list. In such instances a preservation intervention may be recommended.

This may also include 'Trust Center' settings in Microsoft Office that by default prevent the opening of some legacy Office formats without override. If institutional policy is such that these settings cannot be changed, then this may influence the outcome of condition 5.

2) This methodology focuses specifically on file format, however for some use-cases, it may be desirable to consider additional properties beyond file format when making this assessment.

For example, file formats such as AVI, QuickTime MOV and various MPEG video formats are generally considered to not be at immediate risk under these conditions, but these media container formats may store data encoded with less ubiquitous or poorly supported audio and video codecs, which may mean that some file instances will only playback in-part or not at all when using the software provided with a fresh installation of these operating systems.

3) Condition 7 refers to an official web presence. In many cases a file format specification may be published on a source control system such as GitHub as the primary, official web presence.

Current GitHub practice is not to generally remove inactive repositories, so such an official presence may exist but may not have been active or worked upon in many years, and this in turn could mean that security vulnerabilities with a file format or its libraries are present and go unaddressed, or that the file format has otherwise been abandoned.

Further, GitLab previously proposed to remove repositories registered under free user accounts that had been inactive for one year [14]. They didn't implement this policy, however the potential for the re-emergence of this or similar policies on public source control management platforms can signify a risk where such a platform is the sole official source of information about a file format.

As such it may be appropriate to consider additional clauses or time-limits with Condition 7 for public source control platforms where, if the repository has been inactive for a defined period of time or if a critical security vulnerability has been identified and not addressed, the file format may be considered at risk, despite the continuing existence of an official web presence.

4) It is acknowledged that Conditions 7 and 8 refer to a file format's official web presence and that there are other mechanisms for publishing file format descriptions such as books, academic papers and journals, however it is the view of the author that it will be extremely rare in the current age for a file format or its native first-party software to be made available without an accompanying web presence.

5) The file format risk landscape is continually evolving, so it is necessary to repeat such an assessment for a given set of file formats periodically, or in response to a notable change such as a file format standards body dissolving.

V. CONCLUSION

The methodology presented is intended as a practical, generalized and rapid approach to performing file format obsolescence risk assessments.

It is offered as an alternative to complex score-based approaches for quantifying file format obsolescence risk, but the author recognizes that many organizations will prefer such systems, particularly where their preservation practice is already influenced by them.

The nature of the research required to establish the facts around each format currently means that applying this assessment methodology is a manual task, but this will typically provide quicker conclusions than score-based systems.

This methodology has already been used by Preservica to establish a set of 'minimal intervention rulesets,' intended as a ready-made set of preservation policies available to Preservica system users.

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David Clipsham is the File Format Analyst at Preservica, supporting system users in overcoming their file format-related challenges. He previously worked at The National Archives (UK), where among many roles, he spear-headed PRONOM file format research for around 10 years.

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